

Age Up

FALL PREVENTION RESEARCH NEWSLETTER

What do swiss cheese and fall prevention have in common? When they “melt” together, you have a fall prevention success story! For more, please read along.

Study updates

We hope that you are enjoying the remaining days of summer and a sense of normalcy as COVID restrictions lessen. We now have 195+ enrolled volunteers. Thank you to all of you for participating in our study!

The focus of this quarter’s newsletter is “Layers of Defense” in fall prevention. The “Swiss Cheese Model” is used widely to improve hospital patient safety and to stop the spread of COVID and provides a good analogy for fall prevention. The model offers a simple visual to address complex and high stakes hazards.

We are excited to share that a research article, “Older adults’ biobehavioral fall risks were impacted by the COVID pandemic”, was accepted for publication in the *Innovation in Aging* journal. This article highlights that a strong community and social “defense mechanisms” are critical to thrive at any age.

Lastly, September 18–24 is national Fall Prevention Week to raise awareness that falls are preventable!

bit.ly/3wPo3I4

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Balance control and strength as a defense mechanism

Make sure the chair is sturdy and you feel safe performing these exercises before you begin.

1. Hip marching - 5 lifts each leg

Sit upright in a chair and hold the side of the chair. Slowly lift and lower your left leg. Repeat with opposite leg.

2. Upper body twist - 5 times each side

Sit upright in a chair. Cross your arms. Without moving your hips, turn your upper body to the left as far as is comfortable. Hold for 5 seconds. Repeat with opposite side.

3. Ready for a challenge? Mini Squats

Face the back of a sturdy chair and stand with feet shoulder width apart. Slowly bend knees over big toes and back straight as far as is comfortable. Squeeze buttocks as you slowly rise back to standing.

Try more seated and standing exercises like these at:

bit.ly/3AANsX4

Swiss cheese model for fall prevention

Layers of defense mechanisms are needed to prevent a fall

Put a star over your strongest layers of defense. Circle the layers that you could strengthen and write a note on that layer of one step you could take to be stronger.

Swiss cheese model adapted with permission from: Reason, J. (2000). *Human error: models and management*. *BMJ*. 2;320:768-70. doi: 10.1136/bmj.320.7237.768.

Fall prevention can be thought of in terms of the "Swiss Cheese Model" with layers of defense represented by the cheese slices. Each person has a different number of cheese slices (defense mechanisms) and some holes may be bigger than others in each slice (weak link). A person may have poor vision but compensate by creating a safe home environment, using a cane when outside, and building strong balance control to prevent a fall. The more layers of cheese slices a person has will translate to fewer falls.

Safe environment as a defense mechanism

What hazards can you find in this picture? Now look around your environment to see how many hazards you find. How can you modify those hazards or find alternatives? What do you need to make your environment safe?

Hazards: cushions, cat, slipper, plant, magazines, and cords.

FOR MORE INFORMATION:

www.nia.nih.gov/health/fall-proofing-your-home

Working with vision as a defense mechanism

STUDY VOLUNTEERS HAVE SAID:

"I watch for glare and shadows especially on sunny days because my eyes don't adjust to light changes well."

"I know that my depth perception isn't as good as it used to be, so I use my stick to check the depth of the curb."

"I notice that when I wear masks, my double vision gets worse."

For people with low vision, proprioception and other vision impairments, strategies found here can help!

LINK: bit.ly/3wIuAUW

Assistive mobility tools as a defense mechanism

STUDY VOLUNTEERS HAVE SAID:

"I use my walker just in the morning because I know my body is slow to wake up."

"Foldable hiking sticks are helpful. I use it when I come back from the trail."

"I love my cane! I don't bump into people because people give me respectable space and I get to focus on shopping!"